

Ethyl 16-Hydroxy-9 : 10-dibromohexadecenoate (V).—A solution of bromine (1.06 g.) in glacial acetic acid (10 c.c.) was added with constant shaking to a solution of epi-ambrettolic ester (1.7 g.) in glacial acetic acid (20 c.c.). The dibromo ester could not be isolated in a pure state since it liberated bromine even on distillation in vacuum. It was used as such for the oxidation experiments.

15-Aldehyde- Δ^9 -pentadecenoic Acid.—Acetic acid (15 c.c.) was added to the above solution and then a solution of CrO_3 (0.9 g.) in 80% acetic acid (10 c.c.) was added to it drop by drop, the temperature of the mixture being maintained at 80-85° by heating on the water-bath. The addition required about 3½ hours. When the reaction was over, zinc dust (9 g.) was added to it and the mixture heated on the water-bath for 2½ hours more to complete the debromination. It was then filtered and the filtrate extracted thoroughly with ether. The ethereal layer was washed with water and the solvent removed after drying. The residue was hydrolysed with alcoholic potash (20 c.c., 10%) by refluxing on the water-bath for 5 hours. The alcohol was removed on the water-bath by evaporation after addition of successive portions of water. It was then extracted with water to remove neutral matter and then the ice-cold alkaline solution was acidified with cold dilute sulphuric acid. The brownish white precipitate which separated was filtered, washed and dried and crystallised from a mixture of ethyl acetate and petroleum ether and then twice from petroleum ether (b. p. 50-60°) yielding an aldehyde, which is perfectly colourless, m. p. 40-41°. (Found : C, 71.1; H, 9.7. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 71.6; H, 10.4 per cent).

Δ^6 -Tetradecene-1 : 14-dicarboxylic Acid.—Epi-ambrettolic acid (8 g.) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (75 c.c.) by warming slightly on the water-bath. The solution, after cooling was brominated with a solution of bromine (1.75 c.c.) in 25 c.c. of glacial acetic acid. After allowing to stand for some time, the mixture was heated on the water-bath and a solution of CrO_3 (4.6 g.) in 80% acetic acid (25 c.c.) was added to it drop-wise in course of 4 to 5 hours. The mixture was then heated on the boiling water-bath for another hour and then debrominated by heating with zinc dust (25 g.) on the water-bath. The filtrate on dilution with water deposited a solid which was filtered, washed, dried and recrystallised twice from petroleum ether (b. p. 60-70°). It melts at 75-76°. (Found : C, 67.3; H, 9.4. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 67.6; H, 9.9 per cent).

Ethyl Hydrogen- Δ^6 -tetradecene-1 : 14-dicarboxylate (VII).—Epi-ambrettolic ester (12 g.) was dissolved in acetic acid (50 c.c.) and brominated with a solution of bromine (2.5 c.c.) in acetic acid (50 c.c.) and then oxidised with CrO_3 (6 g.) in 80 per cent acetic acid (40 c.c.) as in the previous experiments. It was debrominated with zinc dust (30 g.) at 90-100°. The product was filtered and the filtrate diluted with a large volume of water when the ester-acid separated as an oil. It was taken up with ether and the ethereal layer washed with water to remove chromium salts, dried with anhydrous sodium sulphate and the solvent removed. No solid derivative of the ester acid could be prepared. A portion was hydrolysed with alcoholic potash in the usual way when Δ^6 -tetradecene-1 : 14-dicarboxylic acid was obtained.